

area of Bangladesh. In about 18 basic cropping patterns, rice is grown as the major crop. Where irrigation is available, rice is preferred unless other crops such as wheat, potato, chili, are more advantageous. Under irrigated highland and medium highland situations, the most important cropping patterns are high yield (HYV) boro - HYV t. aman and HYV aus - HYV t. aman, but some farmers may grow a pattern of three rice crops or of a rice - rice - nonrice crop.

In 1978-79, detailed monitoring was done in 62 contiguous farmers' fields in a deep tube well irrigated area at the Salna cropping systems research site of BRRI. Daily record keeping on farmers' field operations and inputs used along with crop-cutting was done to determine input-output of cropping patterns on each plot. The boro crop was irrigated, and the aus and t. aman crops were mainly rainfed. Results indicated (see table) that annual rice production from a hectare of land could vary from 2.3 to 10.3, depending on cropping pattern. Among the single-crop patterns, the HYV boro crop gave the highest production (5 t/ha), net return, and benefit-cost ratio. Among the two-crop patterns, the highest annual production (7.4 t/ha) came from the HYV t. aman - pajam boro pattern, but the highest net return and benefit-cost ratio were from the pajam t. aman - local boro pattern. Among the three-crop patterns, the highest production, net return (\$1,324/ha), and benefit-cost ratio came from the HYV aus - pajam t. aman -

Average productivity, costs, and returns of farmers' rice cropping patterns, Salna rice cropping systems research site, BRRI, 1978-79.

Rice cropping pattern ^a	No. sampled	Total yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
HYV aus	1	2.3	205	120	1.6
Pajam t. aman ^b	3	3.2	141	423	4.3
Local t. aman	2	2.7	242	216	1.9
HYV boro	1	5.0	222	844	4.8
Local boro	1	2.9	235	420	2.8
HYV aus - local t. aman	3	5.5	328	532	2.6
HYV aus - pajam t. aman	2	5.4	268	564	3.1
HYV aus - pajam boro	2	5.9	362	746	3.1
Pajam t. aman - local boro	2	7.0	251	1069	5.3
Pajam t. aman - HYV boro	12	7.3	430	957	3.3
Pajam t. aman - pajam boro	12	6.5	378	927	3.4
HYV t. aman - pajam boro	4	7.4	567	948	2.6
Local aus - pajam t. aman - pajam boro	3	9.2	628	1114	2.8
HYV aus - local t. aman - HYV boro	1	7.6	442	890	3.0
HYV aus - pajam t. aman - local boro	2	9.5	470	1200	3.6
HYV aus - local t. aman - local boro	2	8.0	580	1026	2.8
Local aus - local t. aman - HYV boro	2	5.5	589	489	1.8
HYV aus - pajam t. aman - pajam boro	4	9.9	542	1293	3.4
HYV aus - pajam t. aman - HYV boro	3	10.3	480	1324	3.8

^a HYV = high yielding variety, t = transplanted. ^b Pajam is considered neither a HYV nor a local variety in official statements in Bangladesh.

HYV boro pattern, which also gave the highest production and net return among all the test patterns. The lowest production, net return, and benefit-cost ratio came from the single HYV aus crop. Interestingly the results indicated that the growing of a single HYV boro crop could give higher net return and benefit-cost ratio than those for some two-crop or even some three-crop patterns. Similarly, some two-crop patterns could also give higher

production, net returns, and benefit-cost ratio than some three-crop patterns. Net return and benefit-cost ratio were, of course, influenced by the cost of production and prevailing market price for different rice varieties. The results of the present study may explain why farmers, often called great economists, sometimes do not go for intensive cropping patterns despite irrigation and other facilities. ■

Residual nitrogen fertilizer in soil and its availability in a rice - wheat cropping system

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In a field experiment on a Vertisol, 80 kg N/ha was applied to rice in 3 split doses and to wheat in 2 splits using ¹⁵N-labeled urea. The rice crop used 18.6 kg N/ha, and wheat 22.4 kg (LSD 0.05 = 1.4). Kjeldahl analysis of soil samples

Residual nitrogen fertilizer and its availability. AICRIP, Hyderabad, India.

Crop	Season	Treatment ^a				LSD (0.05)
		Rice-wheat rotation		Wheat-rice rotation		
Rice	1977 wet	¹⁵ N	¹⁵ N			
Wheat	1977-78 dry	0 N	¹⁴ N	¹⁵ N	¹⁵ N	
Rice	1978 wet			0 N	¹⁴ N	
<i>Kg N/ha</i>						
Residual fertilizer N after 1st crop		21.0		18.4		N.S.
Uptake by 2d crop		1.3	1.4	0.4	0.4	0.1

^a¹⁵N = fertilized by labeled urea, ¹⁴N = fertilized with unlabeled urea, 0 N = no N fertilizer added, N.S. = not significant.

drawn from the root zone after harvest showed that the residual nitrogen after rice was 21 kg/ha, and that after wheat

18.4 kg (see table). The KC1-extractable labeled NH₄ + NO₃-N in the root zone amounted to 0.42% of the added nitro-

gen after rice, and 0.09% after wheat. The difference was reflected in the availability of the residual fertilizer nitrogen. Thus, wheat after rice used 6.5% of the fertilizer residue, and rice after wheat

used 2.2%. The effect of the added unlabeled urea (80 kg N/ha) on availability of residual fertilizer nitrogen was negligible in both cases.

The soil and plant samples were ana-

lyzed for $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ isotopic ratio by the International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, using the mass spectrometric and modified Dumas methods, respectively. ■

Announcements

Dr. M. Mahadevappa receives Hooker Award for agricultural research

The Academic Council of the Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi, recently presented the Hooker Award for 1978-79 to Dr. M. Mahadevappa, plant scientist (paddy), Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya (University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore).

The award was presented at the IARI convocation on 28 February 1981 for Dr. Mahadevappa's outstanding research contributions in the area of rice breeding and in the development of high-yielding rice varieties. ■

M. Mahadevappa, recipient of the 1978-79 Hooker Award for Agricultural Research.

Dr. Amir U. Khan receives award from Indian Society of Agricultural Engineers

The Indian Society of Agricultural Engineers (ISAE) recently presented the Commendation Medal for 1979-80 to Dr. Amir U. Khan, IRRI agricultural engineer with the IRRI-PAK Industrial Development Project, Islamabad, Pakistan. The ISAE award recognized Dr. Khan's outstanding contributions in the field of farm machinery research and development. A Life Member of ISAE, Dr. Khan has been an agricultural engineer for 25 years. He is former head of the IRRI Agricultural Engineering Department and project leader, USAID/IRRI Agricultural Machinery Development Project. Dr. Khan has also received the Presidential Gold

Amir Khan checks an IRRI experimental machine in a rice field.

Medal of the Philippine Inventors Commission. He has published about 50 research papers and technical articles on

mechanization of tropical agriculture and appropriate technology for developing countries. ■

